

The Analysis of Implicature and Cooperation Principles in Animation Web Drama a Day Before us: Pragmatic Study

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ABSTRACT: This research aims 1) to find the types of implicature and examine the realization of the cooperative principle found in animated web drama speech, 2) to examine the realization of the cooperative principle found in animated web drama speech. The success of communication can be seen in the use of language in relation to context (pragmatics) and it is also not uncommon in films, and there are many implied meanings expressed in the form of implicatures to be conveyed. This research used Grice's theory (1975) of cooperative principles and implicatures. The data used speech and conversational dialogues that contain forms of implicatures and cooperative principles. The research method used qualitative. Based on the results of the analysis, 7 data of conventional implicatures were found and 14 data of conversational implicatures. The form of the principle of cooperation from the observance of the maxims was found in 10 data 4 maxims of quality, 1 maxim of quantity, 2 maxims of relevance, 3 maxims of manner and the manifestation of the principle of cooperation from violation of the maxims was found in 11 data 3 maxims of quantity, 5 maxims of relevance, 3 maxim of way).

KEYWORDS: Cooperation principles, Implicature, Pragmatic, Web drama.

INTRODUCTION

Language is used to convey a meaning or purpose and sometimes the meaning has a direct or indirect meaning (Rahman & Lewa). A speaker in carrying out a conversation should fulfill the rules in conversation, so that the intent of the purpose is easily understood by the speech partner or listener and it results in something implicit or implicit in the use of language (Mey, 1993).

Levinson (1983) argued that pragmatics is the study of relationships between language and context that are grammatical or encoded in the structure of language. Levinson also stated that pragmatics is the study of the relationship between language and context, mainly seeing that context plays an important role in the study of pragmatics because it is the study of language use. It also includes implicatures and cooperative principles in pragmatics.

Djajasudarma (2012) asserted that pragmatics is the study of the interaction between linguistic knowledge and knowledge bases about the world that belong to speakers and speech partners (readers or listeners). The use of appropriate language has a very good influence on the relationship between speech participants (Tahir et al., 2022; Taguchi, 2011). Therefore, it is necessary to apply the principle of cooperation in a conversation (Geurts, 2010; Sukmawaty et al., 2022).

Furthermore, Implicature is also very common in everyday conversation. Implicature is used to explain the meaning of the implications that are behind what is said or written as something that is implied. An understanding of implicature is absolutely necessary to be able to understand the implied meaning in an utterance (Schwenter, 2014). There are two types of implicature, namely conventional implicature and conversational implicature. Both types of implicature have their own criteria in understanding an utterance. Conventional implicature is an implicature that is known by everyone, while conversational implicature is an implicature that is only known by certain people who know about the context of the speech (Geurts, 2009; Andini et al., 2021). The context is thing or element whose existence really supports communication, both for the speaker and the listener depending on the situation of the utterance (Yuniarti, 2014; Adinda et al., 2022).

In films and dramas, there are many dialogues involving speakers and speech partners where the communication occurs which basically has a specific purpose and objective for the listener to understand what the speaker express through the speech (Burry, 2011; Syawal et al., 2022). Without understanding the meaning of the utterance, it will not run smoothly.

Web Dramas are short dramas with episodes ranging from 10 to 16 episodes and generally lasting 15-45 minutes per episode (Kang, 2017; Jariah et al., 2022). Web drama is drama that have a shorter duration than regular Korean dramas. Web dramas can be an alternative choice to watch Korean dramas which tend to be short in duration. Apart from that, web dramas usually have lighter plots and are refreshing to watch (Kang, 2021; Adinda et al., 2021).

The conversation in the animated web drama A Day Before Us allows for hidden intentions to be conveyed through the form of implicature and the realization of the principle of cooperation in communication that occurs in conversational communication between these characters. In raising this topic, the research aims to find out more clearly about the implicature contained in the dialogue of the animated web drama A Day Before Us.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVE

This research formulated two objectives, 1) to find the types of implicatures and examine the realization of the cooperative principle found in animated web drama speech, 2) to examine the realization of the cooperative principle found in animated web drama speech.

METHOD

The researcher used the qualitative method using the descriptive approach. It aims to obtain a complete description of a subject with respect to the person studied. Furthermore, it deals with the ideas, perceptions, opinions or beliefs of the people studied, not all of which can be quantified (Basuki, 2006). The data criterion in qualitative research is specific data. The data that is specific is the data that actually happens as it is, not the data that is just seen, talked about, but the data that contains the meaning behind what is seen and said (Sugiyono, 2007).

The data source for this research is the animated web drama A Day Before Us. This research took samples of sentences, utterances and conversational dialogues that contain implicatures in the animated web drama and used note-and-listen techniques.

Source of data is done by collecting information through sources, namely literature, books, journals, to previous research and sites on the internet that are considered capable of providing the information and data needed in conducting this research. Furthermore, the research activities carried out to find and study sources of information in the form of previous studies, references and documents related to the research topic.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Based on the analysis of implicatures and the principles of cooperation in the animated web drama A Day Before Us, the results showed that there were 21 implicatures and 21 forms of cooperation principles found. The implicature is divided into two types that are 7 conventional implicature data and 14 unconventional or conversational implicature data. Furthermore, the form of the principle of cooperation is divided into two classifications, namely; 10 data on compliance with cooperative principles and 11 data on violations of cooperative principles. In the classification of forms of cooperation compliance that there are 10 maxims found namely; 4 data maxims of quality, 1 data maxims of quantity, 2 data maxims of relevance and 3 data maxims of manner. In the form of violation of cooperation that there are 11 maxims found namely; 3 data maxims of quantity, 5 data maxims of relevance, and 3 data maxims of manner.

Conventional Implicature (규약 함축 “gyuyak hamchuk”)

Conventional implicature is an implicature that is obtained directly from the meaning of the word, not from the principle of conversation. In conventional implicature, the implications and meanings are general in nature, so that the meaning and implications of an utterance can be understood by everyone in general.

Data 1

Yeorem : 그나저나 가을인데 날씨가 뭐야래.
“Genajeona gaerinde nalssiga
mwo irae..”
What the hell is the weather

Wook : like this in autumn
: 네말이...
“Ne mari...”
Yes I said...
(Season 1 episode 4)

The context in the data above is, where Yeorem "여름" (speaker) and Wook "욱" the speech partners were sitting on a ladder and at that time Yeorem was grumbling because of the hot weather.

From the conversation, it is found in the utterances of 그나저나 가을인데 날씨가 뭐야래 [Genajeona gaerinde nalssiga mwo irae] “What the hell is the weather like this in autumn”. The utterance contains conventional implicature, which is stated by convention and common knowledge that in early autumn the weather during the day is hot. So the implication that arises is that at the beginning of autumn the weather is still hot because it is just the change from summer to autumn. Through this explanation, it can be concluded that the meaning contained in the implicature has the meaning of affirming.

Data 2
Yeorem : 자. 그럼 우리 건배할까
: Ja..gereom uri
geobegalkka!”
: Fine..then let's toast!
(Season 1 episode 4)

The context in the data above is regarding Yeorem who was gathering with his friends and celebrating the meeting by drinking alcohol, Yeorem asked his friends to make a toast.

The speech delivered by Yeorem has the meaning of a toast to celebrate them being able to gather. These utterances include conventional implicatures which are stated by an agreement or convention that Korean people no longer generally celebrate anything with a bias for drinking alcohol, and toasts can be said to be mandatory things that must be done when drinking alcohol, this is done by collecting their glasses in the middle then with in unison they will say 'ccan' (cheers). Furthermore, it is very common and is known by everyone. Through this explanation, it can be concluded that the meaning contained in the implicature has the meaning of governing.

Data 3
Yeorem : 야 가만히 좀 있어. 자꾸
움직이면 그럴 수가 없잖아
“Ya gamanhi jom
isseo!jakku umjikimyeon
geril suga eopjanha”
: Hey don't move I can't
draw you if you keep
moving
(Season 1 episode 8)

The context in the data above found that Yeorem is drawing Wook and he asks Wook to be quiet because he always moves when he is being drawn. He is an art major who is skilled at drawing, so Wook asks Yeorem to draw him.

The speech delivered by yeorem means that a picture will be good if it goes through a good process. The drawing will be good if the person being drawn cooperates but before Yeorem finishes drawing, the wook is always moving. The speech delivered by him regarding the command to be silent while being drawn is already known by many people related to the meaning contained in the speech. Therefore, the speech delivered by yeorem is included in conventional implicature. Through this explanation, it can be

concluded that the meaning contained in the implicature has the meaning of governing.

Data 4

Wook : 출겼다. 따뜻할 때 마셔
“Chupgettda..ttattethal tte
masyeo.”
: Cold.. drink while warm

The context in the data above is about Wook who was sitting in the park with his friends, and it was winter so Wook gave a warm drink to his friend.

This utterance includes conventional implicature which is stated by the general knowledge that something warm is indeed very suitable to drink in cold weather. Therefore, the speech delivered by Wook is included in the conventional implicature. Through this explanation, it can be concluded that the meaning contained in the implicature has the meaning of governing.

Implicature

Unconventional/conversational (대화 함축/ “daehwa hamchuk”

Unconventional implicature or commonly also called conversational implicature is an implicature that is only known by people who know or understand the context of the speech. It should be noted that this conversational implicature has a communicative meaning or the intent of the speaker. Therefore, the meaning in conversational implicature cannot be understood based on what is said, but based on the context around the utterance.

Data 5

Haeun : 여름아너 취했어..
“Yeorema neo
chihaesseo...”
Yeorem you're already
drunk...
Yeorem : 아니야 아직 안 취했어. 짠
“aniya ajik an
chihaesseo..ccan”
Not yet I'm not
drunk..cheers
(Season 1 episode 2)

The data above is about Haeun and Yeorem being out and celebrating a meeting by drinking alcohol. Haeun and Yeorem are classmates but Haeun is older than Yeorem, moreover, at that time Haeun saw Yeorem was drunk enough so he told Yeorem that he was already drunk).

Conversational implicature can be seen through the utterances of 여름아너 취했어 [Yeorema neo chihaesseo] is utterances addressed to Yeorem. The real meaning of this story is because Yeorem already seems unable to control his consciousness due to drunkenness, and has exceeded his capacity to consume alcohol and Haeun as an older sibling also feels responsible for that. The implication of this speech is that Haeun (speaker) asks Yeorem (partner) to stop drinking. Yeorem could understand the implicature in Haeun's speech because he knew the context of the conversation that took place in other words this speech indirectly implied the meaning that Haeun wanted Yeorem to stop drinking alcohol because he was drunk enough. Through this explanation, it can be concluded that the meaning contained in the implicature has the meaning of governing.

Data 6

Yeorem : 옥아~~ 나취해 사아.
“Okaa ~~ na chihae sa.”
Wooka I'm drunk
어..!
“Eo..!”
What 'surprise'
(Season 1 episode 2)

The data above is about Yeorem and Wook exchanging messages. At that time, Yeorem was out and having a meeting with his friends so he celebrated by drinking alcohol. Meanwhile, Wook was at home until finally Yeorem felt drunk and sent a message to Wook.

Conversational implicature can be seen through the utterance 옥아~~ 나취해사아 [Okaa ~~ na chihae sa] is an utterance addressed to Wook. The real meaning of this statement was because Yeorem was very drunk and he might not be able to go home alone, and sent a message to Wook, instead of ordering him to pick him up, Yeorem only said that he was drunk. However, Wook can understand the implicature in Yeorem's speech because he knows the context of the conversation that took place. The implication of this story is that Yeorem (the speaker) asked Wook (his partner) to pick him up. In other words, this speech indirectly implies that Yeorem wants Wook to pick him up because he is already very drunk, and can't go home by himself. Through this explanation, it can be concluded that the meaning contained in the implicature has the meaning of governing.

Data 7

Yeonwo : 한 입만 먹자. ?
“Han ibman meokja..”
Let me eat a little..?
:내꺼야!
“Nae kkeoya!”
This is mine!
(Season 1 episode 4)

The context in the data above is about Wook and Yeonwo who are sitting in the campus garden. Wook is holding a snack in his hand and Yeonwo wants to ask for the food Wook brought)

Conversational implicature can be seen from the speech of 내꺼야! [Nae kkeoya!] is the answer to a question raised by Yeonwo. The utterance 'This is mine' implies refusing to give her even a small amount of food. In other words, this speech indirectly implies that Wook does not want Yeonwo to ask for the food he is holding. Through this explanation, it can be concluded that the meaning contained in the implicature has the meaning of rejecting.

Data 8

Heun : 그런데 오늘 덥지 않나?
"Gereonde onel deopji anhni?"
By the way isn't it hot today?
(Season 1 episode 5)

The data above is about Haeun who had just finished his class and then went to his friends who were already in the canteen, his friends who were already in the canteen offered what Haeun wanted to order).

Conversational implicature can be seen through the utterances of 그런데 오늘 덥지 않나? [Gereonde onel deopji anhni?] is a speech

addressed to his friend. The real meaning of the statement was because Yeorem had just finished his class and then caught up with his friend who was already in the canteen first, his friend then offered him what menu he wanted to order, but instead of mentioning the menu he wanted, Haeun said that today's weather hot. The implication of this utterance is that Haeun (the speaker) asked his friend to order a cold menu. His friend could understand the implicature in Haeun's speech because his friend knew the context of the conversation that took place. In other words, this speech indirectly implies the meaning that Haeun wants his friend to order a cold menu because the weather that day was hot. Through this explanation, it can be concluded that the meaning contained in the implicature has the meaning of affirming.

Data 9

Wook : 어제 술 마셨어?
“Eoje sul masyeosseo?”
Did you drink yesterday?
내가 너야!
“Naega neoya!”
Yeowo : I am you!
(Season 1 episode 5)

The data above is regarding Wook and Yeonwo who

were in the cafeteria, He ordered a menu that he wasn't used to eating, and that felt strange to Wook because Yeonwo didn't usually eat things he didn't really like.

Conversational implicature can be seen from the speech of **내가 너야**[Indeed I am you], it showed the answer to the Wook question. The true meaning of this speech is an insinuation directed by Wook, that he doesn't seem to like drinking very much and does it every day. The implication of this story is that Yeonwo (partner) insinuated Wook (speaker) that he doesn't like drinking alcohol like him. Wook can understand the implicature in Yeonwo's speech because he knows the context of the conversation that took place. Through this explanation, it can be concluded that the meaning contained in the implicature has the meaning of denying.

Data 10

Wook : 누나애 말하는 거 봤어요?
“Nuna yae malhanen geo
bwasseoyo?”
Brother, have you ever seen him
talk?
Hauen 로.
“Byeollo..”
I am you!
(Season 1 episode 5)

Regarding Haeun, Wook, and also Yeonwo who were in the canteen like the context in the show above. Haeun and Wook exchanged stories but Yeonwo was just silent in front of them, they were friends but Haeun and Yeonwo had not joined their friendship for a long time. Therefore there is still awkwardness between them.

Conversational implicature can be seen from the speech of **누나애 말하는 거 봤어요** [Nuna yae malhanen geo bwasseoyo] which was the question asked to Wook. The real intention of this story is as a form of satire to the quiet Yeonwo. The utterance of ‘Brother have you ever seen him talk’ had the implication that he was insinuating Yeonwo to talk more and don't just stay silent when someone is having a nice conversation, he should have joined in the story so the atmosphere wouldn't feel awkward. Through this explanation, it can be concluded that the meaning contained in the implicature has a mocking meaning.

Principles of Cooperation (협력 원리/ Hyeopryeok Wonri)

Grice suggests that good conversation is it can serve its purpose. Therefore, to achieve this goal, Grice (1975) includes four basic maxims of conversation as utterances towards effective cooperation in the use of language, or what is better known as the principle of cooperation. But not infrequently the principle of cooperation is violated by speakers in dialogue. This sub-chapter will describe the compliance and violation of the principle of cooperation by describing what maxims are found in the dialogues of the characters in this web drama.

Adhering to Cooperation Principles (협력원칙준수/Hyeopryeok Wonchik Junsu)

Data 11

- Wook : 혼자 밥 먹으러 왔어요? 여름이는데요?
“Honja bab meokereo
wasseoyo?Yeoreminenyo?
You eat alone? Where's
- Hauen : Yeorem?
아 여름이. 주별 과제 모임 끝나고서
온데.
“Ah Yeoremi..jubyel gwaje
moim gettnagoseo onde”.
Ah Yeorem..he will come after
his team's project meeting.
(Season 1 episode 5)

The data above shows that in the conversation Wook asked Haeun because he just came alone to the canteen and where was Yeorem who was always with him. Haeun gave relevant answers to these answers, so Wook who asked immediately understood that Haeun was only temporarily alone there because Yeorem would catch up with Haeun after his business was finished later. Haeun's speech can be said to have obeyed the maxim of relevance.

Data 12

- Wook : 근데 여름이는 오래 걸린대요?
“Gende yeoreminen orae
geollindaeyo?”
But did Yeorem come too late?
- Hauen : 아니 금방 온다는 것 같던데.
“Ani gembang ondanen geot
gathdeonde.”
No, he said he'd be here quickly.
(Season 1 episode 5)

The data above shows that in the conversation Wook asked Haeun if Yeorem would come late. Haeun gave the answer straightforwardly and clearly. So Wook understands that Haeun will be coming soon. Haeun's speech can be said to have obeyed the maxim of manner.

Data 13

- A : 뭐 하나. 답다면서?
“Mwo
hanya..deopdameonseo?
What are you doing..you said
hot?

“Ah Yeorema..anyeong”

Ah Yeorem..hi

(Season 2 episode 1)

Based on the data above, the conversation took place on the stairs leading to class, Yeorem accidentally saw Haeun and Wook. B's speech “Haeun” violates the maxim of relevance. This is because the contents of Haeun's speech are irrelevant to the topic of conversation asked by his partner "Yeorem". Yeorem's speech contains questions about things to do, while Haeun's answer is to greet. There is no connection between the question and the answer. Of course the answer Haeun expected was what they were doing here. So, it can be concluded that Haeun's speech in conversation violates the maxim of relevance.

Data 17

Haeun : 누나 수업이 끝났어요?
“Nuna sueopi kkethnasseoyo?”
Have you finished your class?
Yeonwo 응 이제 막 끝났어. 오래 기다렸지.
미안해
“Eng, ije mak kketnasseoyo..oraeg
gidaryeottji. Mianhae
Yes, now it's over.. I've been
waiting for a long tme. I'm sorry
(Season 2 episode 1)

Based on the data above, the conversation occurred when Yeonwo was talking to Haeun by telephone to ask whether the class Haeun was taking had finished or not. Speech B “Haeun” (Yes, it's over now.. I've been waiting for a long time. I'm sorry), violates the maxim of quantity. Since Haeun's speech can be categorized as exaggerated. The contributions made in the conversation in the speech fragments are not in accordance with what is needed, namely too much. So, it can be concluded that Haeun's speech in conversation violates the maxim of quantity.

Data 18

Haeun : 이름이 뭐예요?
“Iremi mwoyeyo?”
What's your name?
Wook 저는 김옥입니다.
“Jeonen Kim Wook imnida”
My name is Kim Wook.
(Season 2 episode 5)

The data above showed that the conversation occurred when Haeun and Wook were sitting in a park near the campus to discuss each other's activities during the holidays. B's speech "Wook" violates the maxim of relevance. That's because the contents of Wook's speech are irrelevant to the topic of conversation asked by the speaker "Haeun". Haeun's speech contained questions about news, while Wook's answer was a statement that he was only at home all the time. There is no connection between the question and the answer. Of course the answer Haeun expected was 'good' or 'bad' news. So, it can be concluded that Wook's speech in conversation violates the maxim of relevance.

Data 19

- Yeonwo : 머리에 분홍색은 말고 있는 거예요?
“Meorie bunhongsaecken malgo ittnen geoyeyo?”
Why are you wearing something pink in your hair?
- Haeun : 아 이거 여자들한테는 필수템이야
“Ah igeo yeojadel gantenen philsuthemiya”
Ah this is something important for women
(Season 2 episode 6)

Based on the data above, the conversation occurred when Yeonwo and Haeun were sitting facing each other and doing a task together, at that time Haeun was wearing hair rolls in her bangs. B's speech “Haeun” violates the maxim of manner. Since Haeun's speech was unclear about what was being asked and even seemed ambiguous. So, it can be concluded that Haeun's speech in conversation violates the maxim of manner.

Data 20

- Geonha : 남자 친구야?
“Namja chinguya?”
Your boyfriend?
- Haeun : 아니요 아 그러니까 그 같은 과제 한 동생 동생이에요
“Aniyo! Ah geronikka ge gathen gwaje han dongsaengieyo”.
No! Ah, this is how doing assignments together, yes, younger siblings.
(Season 2 episode 6)

The data 20 showed that the conversation took place when Haeun and Yeonwo were sitting and doing a task together, then Geonha (Haeun's classmate) came up to them. B's speech “Haeun” (No! Ah, this is how doing assignments together, yes underclassmen) violates the maxim of quantity. Moreover, Haeun's speech can be categorized as excessive. Contributions donated in the conversation in the speech are not in accordance with what is needed. Haeun should just simply answer the question with "yes my boyfriend" or "no". So, it can be concluded that Haeun's speech in conversation violates the maxim of quantity.

CONCLUSION

This research discussed the types of implicature and the form of cooperation principles in the dialogue of the animated web drama A Day Before Us.

Based on the presentation of the results obtained, the types of implicature found include 7 data containing conventional implicatures where the meaning uttered by the speaker can be understood by the audience even because the meaning is general in nature. Conversational implicature in the speech of the animated web drama A Day Before Us found as many as 14 data, this indicates that the most unconventional types of implicature or conversational implicature are found in the dialogue of this animated web drama. Based on this research, it can also be concluded that there were compliance and violations of the cooperative principle that occurred

in the conversation. Communication is a means of how we can socialize in society, therefore in communicating there is a principle of cooperation that we must obey. In addition to compliance, violations of the cooperative principle in communication are also legal if they are committed.

Based on the results of the research show that there are 10 data on the form of adherence to the principles of cooperation in the web drama dialogue utterances. Namely, with details of 4 forms of compliance with the maxim of quality, 1 form of compliance with the maxim of quantity, 2 forms of compliance with the maxim of relevance, and 3 forms of compliance with the maxim of manner. The form of obeying the principle of cooperation that was found the most was the form of obeying the principle of cooperation on the maxim of quality. Forms of violations of the principle of cooperation in the animated web drama found as many as 11 data. Details of 3 forms of violation of the principle of cooperation in the maxim of quantity, and 5 forms of violation of the principle of cooperation in the maxim of relevance, violation of the principle of cooperation in the maxim of manner is 3 forms. The results obtained state that the most common form of violation of the cooperative principle is the violation of the cooperative principle of the maxim of relevance.

REFERENCES

1. Adinda, Rahman, F., & Akhmar, A.M. (2021). Penerapan Metode Tadashi Suzuki pada Proses Latihan Teater: Kajian Ketubuhan Aktor, Lakon I La Galigo. *IsoLEC Proceedings*, 5(1), 167-177.
2. Adinda, Rahman, F., Akhmar, A.M. & Indriati Lewa. (2022). Analisis Naskah “Kereta Kencana” Karya Ws Rendra. *CaLLs (Journal of Culture, Arts, Literature, and Linguistics)*, 1(2), 56-67.
3. Andini, C., Yassi, A., & Sukmawaty. (2021). The Use of Honorifics in English and Buginese with Special Reference to Bone Language: A Comparative Study. *International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology*, 6(7), 873-877.
4. Basuki, A. (2006). *Metode Bayes*. PENSITS, Surabaya.
5. Burry, A. (2011). *Multi-mediated Dostoevsky. Transposing Novels into Opera, Film, and Drama (Vol. 1)*. Northwestern University Press.
6. Djajasudarma, F. (2012). *Wacana dan Pragmatik. Bandung*: Refika Aditama.
7. Geurts, B. (2009). Scalar Implicature and Local Pragmatics. *Mind & Language*, 24(1), 51-79.
8. Geurts, B. (2010). *Quantity Implicatures*. Cambridge University Press.
9. Jariah, R. A., Rahman, F., & P Amir, M. (2022). Social Problems in Drama 13 Reasons Why: Peirce Semiotics Approach. *TEKSTUAL*, 20(1), 48-60.
10. Grice, H.P. (1975). *Logic and Conversation. In Cole, P & Morgan, J. (eds.) Syntax and Semantics, vol3*. New York: Academic Press.
11. Kang, J.M. (2007). Just another Platform for Television? The Emerging Web Dramas as Digital Culture in South Korea. *Media, Culture, & Society*, 39(5), 762-772.
12. Kang, J.M. (2021). Better than Television: The Rise of Korean Korean Web Dramas. *International Journal of Cultural Studies*, 24(6), 993-1008.
13. Levinson, S.C., Levinson, S.C., & Levinson, S. (1983). *Pragmatics*. Cambridge University Press.
14. Mey, J.L. (1993). *Pragmatics: An Introduction*. Oxford: Blackwell Publishers.
15. Rahman, F. Lewa, I. (2021). The Potential of Children’s Literature in Education and Environmental Ethics: Linguistics and Literary Approaches. *The 1st International Conference on Research in Social Sciences and Humanities (ICoRS 2020)*, Atlantis Press.
16. Schwenter, S. (2014). *Pragmatics of Conditional Marking: Implicature, Scalarity, and Exclusivity*. Routledge.
17. Sugiyono. (2007). *Metode Penelitian Bisnis*. Bandung: Alfabeta
18. Yuniarti, N. (2014). Implikatur Percakapan dalam Percakapan Himor. *Jurnal Pendidikan Bahasa*, 3(2), 225-240.
19. Sukmawaty, Rahman, F.F. & Andini, C. (2022). Covid-19 Pandemic and Axiology of Communication: A Study of Linguistic Phenomena. *IJISRT*, 7(4), 1079-1087.
20. Syawal, L.O.M.I., Rahman, F., & Amir p, M. (2022). Social Condition of French Society Pre-revolution in A Tale of Two Cities Novel by Charles Dickens, *TEKSTUAL*, 20(1), 37-47.

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21. Tahir, M.D., Tahir, M., Rahman, F., & Latjuba, A.Y. (2022). Cultural Discourse in Indonesian Humor: A Case Study of Some Short Dialogues. *Theory and Practice in Language Studies*, 12(5), 1009-1018.
 22. Taguchi, N. (2011). Teaching Pragmatics: Trends and Issues. *Annual Review of Applied Linguistics*, 31, 289-310.

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